

Parental Involvement And Academic Performances Of Grade 7 Students

Julieth Valenzuela Leander¹, Frederick Edward T. Fabella²

^{1,2}FEU Roosevelt Graduate School Cainta, Rizal, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study is focused on the Parental Involvement and the Academic Performances of Grade 7 students in Marikina High School, Relatively this study discussed the level of Parental Involvement in terms of Epstein's six types of Parental Involvement. It Identified the relationship between the level of Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of the students by getting their General Weight Average for the second grading period. This research followed the Descriptive relational research design to determine the relationship between the Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of Grade 7 Students in Marikina High School.

The Systematic Cluster Sampling procedures were utilized in this study, there were 265 respondents (Parents of students) from 7 sections of 20 sections for Grade 7 level of Marikina High School, School Year 2019- 2020.

In order to obtain the pertinent data for this study, the department part of the students' report card was used as it showed the academic performance . On the other hand, a Likert Scale Questionnaire was used to identify the level of Parental Involvement to categorize the Parental Involvement (at home and school) The researcher used an instrument adapted and modified based on Epsteins' Framework on Parental Involvement, which underwent subsequent expert content validation.

The profile variables of the parents were also considered and correlated with the level of Parental Involvement. In terms of educational attainment parents, who finished high school had the largest frequency followed by elementary graduates and the rest were able to get higher level of education. In terms of Gender female parents or guardians mostly answered the survey or questionnaire. The parents with the age of 30-35 got the highest frequency. In terms of socio – economic status it showed that average monthly salary of family was about 11,000- 15,999 who got the highest percentage out of 265 parent- respondents.

The level of Parental involvement consisted of two variables (school and home). The Level of parental involvement at home in terms of parenting, learning at home, decision making and communicating indicated that the parents were frequently involved except for decision making where the parents agreed that they sometimes participated in the decision about school matters. The level of Involvement of Parents in school such as volunteering, collaborating , decision making and for communicating was also frequent. Similarly, the academic performance of the students were significantly correlated with the level of parental involvement at school. The age and educational attainment of parents were significantly correlated with the level of involvement of parents in the education of their children at home. The Parental involvement was moderately high level and the academic performance of grade 7 students was moderately satisfactorily in their class in grade 7. The findings of this study implies that Parental Involvement is very important to achieve the academic performance of students, especially those who were found to have unsatisfactory grades. The school could work in collaboration with the parents with the end view of bringing about improvement in the academic performance of the students.

It is thus recommended that school should consider coming up with activities, projects or programs that will entice the parents to volunteer to be part of the said activity / project or program. It is also recommended that open communication be enhanced among parents, children and teacher to establish rapport. Guidance Counselor may take integrative programs to support the efforts of parents and teachers when it comes to academic performance of students. The school should consider conducting seminar / workshop for the parents on the use of technology and online spaces resources as a potential new formats to support parental involvement.

INTRODUCTION

Parental involvement in the child's education has always been discussed in and out of the academe, both as rhetoric and a phenomenon. Parental involvement in the child's education garnered support over the years as it is a factor that affects the academic successes of children. (Castro, Expósito-Casas, López-Martín, Lizasoain, Navarro-Asencio, & Gaviria, 2015). But the reality of parental involvement, specifically in Philippine context must be studied further as drastic changes in behaviors relating to family, parenting and its indirect effect to the child's academic success and behavior are displayed in school. (Alampay, 2014).

There is an actual evidence or proof in school concerning lack of parental involvement and its effect. These are the testimonies from the class advisers or subject teachers every time the attention of parents are called they use "Call Slip form" from guidance office, issued by the adviser or subject teacher more often, parents don't show up because they are working, too much busy in their businesses and no one attends to the needs of their young child, A proof of lack of parental involvement is the lower number of parents who participate during every Parent-Teacher Conference, Out of 40 class number, the actual number of parents during meeting or any school activities is just about 30% of the parents, and Lastly most of the parents are not interested to get the report card of their children, They did not get the chance of meeting the teachers of their children to know their standing in class or any problem inside the school. There is no communication between the teachers and parents and this is the reason why some students have remained a problem in school proper remediation or intervention regarding academic performance.

The chosen topic I had it shows Parents have underestimated the importance of Parental Involvement in a busy world of today, Lack of concern in terms of parental involvement is manifested in the performance of their children academic, attitudes, family problem early pregnancy, pre-marital sex and drop outs. Parents are not aware of the domino effect if the parents just show their involvement in terms of the student's academic performance.

Family is a fundamental factor that contributes to the development of the child, since it is the first social and educational environment that he or she encounters. Parental connection capitulate pupils enhanced performance in school; thus families must ascertain a supportive home environment for their children as learners. This study surveyed the influences of parent-supported using Epstein's framework on the different parenting styles and on its effect on bridging the gap between parents, pupils and school routine. It also viewed on parents' socioeconomic status and educational attainment to verify if these could affect the parental involvement.

Therefore, a conducive environment is beneficial as students start to learn. (Porumbu, & Necşoi, 2013). This also touches on the fact that educational influences from the parents may manifest through the child's performance at school, through the behaviors that they have modeled at home or through their guidance. Direct or indirectly, parental involvement is a fundamental force that shapes the not only the personality, emotional capacity of children, but also their academic acumen that usually translate to their school performance. (Khajehpour, & Ghazvini, 2011). Being mindful with the localized context of parental involvement in the Philippine setting, and being sensitive with the cultural dynamics at play, this study aims to paint a clear picture on how the nuances of parental involvement and its effects on academic performance can be translated into actionable data.

Background of the Study

This study focused on the rhetoric of parental involvement, how it affects the academic performance of Grade 7 students in the local setting, most specifically in the Philippine context as the educational system is continuously improving on assimilating the K12 program. This study was also focused in this Grade as it is when the children show transitions from childhood to adolescence, This is a unique period for both the parents and their involvement to the child's education and the child's academic performance.

The reality of parental involvement in the Philippine context is quite different from what several western and Asian contemporary studies suggest. In the Philippines, it was noted by front line teachers that parents tend to be uninvolved with their children and their academic performance. Through discourse, some parents unconsciously subscribe to the belief that it was not their primary responsibility to be involved with the children's schooling; that it was their children's teacher's responsibility to ensure that their children perform well (Blair, 2014).

Academic Performance is also one of the important issues for parents. It is important for the parents to send their children to school and to monitor their children's academic performance. In particular, parents are worried whether their children are performing according to their potential, having good study habits and if they are doing their homework, attending classes, and showing appropriate behavior towards school.

There are so many factors that can be attributed to such beliefs, as culturally, many parents nowadays are primarily

concerned with their finances and economic capabilities. In some instances, there are also parents that are not prepared for the responsibility of having a child of their own, while some have no other choice but to work abroad and be away from their children for years, decades even (Arguillas, & Williams, 2010).

On the other hand, there is also the nuance when the children are resisting their parents' control over their expectations on their academic performance (Bernardo, 2010).

Parenting

Parental involvement and academic performance have always been at the heart of research of school psychologist and educators. Studies have shown that the two construct is positively related to each other, with most findings demonstrating that parent's involvement with their child's education has benefited them, as stakeholder, the children as their learners and the school as institution. (Khajehpour, 2011; Al-Awan, 2014; Marshall & Jackman, 2015). Parents are agents of change in securing the foundations for their child's learning capabilities and educational achievement (Kimaro, & Machumu, 2015; Perez, 2018). Recent study also confirmed that parental involvement in terms of support to their child's educational goals & achievement, their academic socialization also helped. (Benner, Boyle, & Sadler, 2016). It is also noted that the more the parents check on the child's school performance such as homework, participation with extracurricular activities, and are engaged with the school themselves with parent teacher meetings, the better their children perform in school. (Rafiq, et al 2013).

In that same sense, parents guide their children to develop a plan for their future just like what programs or careers are prepared to encourage the learners to respond positively. (Jolly & Matthews, 2012). This could be attributed to factors such as parental annulment or separation, working abroad, early demise of one of the parents or both parents, both parents have new families so children grow up in single-parent families or live with a stepfather or stepmother or grandparents as part of their childhood. In this study the cares of most of the 265 students were left to their mothers and/or female guardians, This explained why female parents outnumbered the male parents. Many studies highlighted that mothers were engaged in their children's education more frequently than fathers (Duursma, 2014; Kim and Hill, 2015; Baker, 2018),

There are times that student feels that they are not being trusted by their parents when the latter are too involved (Llamas & Tuazon, 2016). Although parental involvement is related to many positive academic performances in their children, it may also bring about high levels of anxiety and depression if not developmentally appropriate. (Fingerman, Cheng, Wesselmann, Zarit, Furstenberg, & Birditt, 2012). Studies show that students with over controlling parents, or those whom they identify as helicopter parents have significantly higher levels of anxiety, depression and less satisfaction with life. This negative effect on the students are largely explained by the perceived violation of the students need for autonomy, independence and competence. (Schiffrin, Liss, Miles-McLean, Geary, Erchull, & Tashner, 2014).

Academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks of a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time. These goals are measured by using continuous assessment or examinations results (Narad and Abdullah, 2016).

Previous studies have found that improvement in the academic performance of students is dependent on a combination of teacher, student, school and parental factors (Amuzu et al, 2017).

Moreover, the size of a class or students to teacher ratio has also been found as a school factor which influence academic performance (Ajani and Akinyele 2014). There is a significant relationship between teacher to students' ratio and a student's performance in Mathematics. (Zyngier 2014). argued that if the class size is smaller and is combined with effective teaching, its impact on the academic performance is positive.

The location of a school has also been found to have a significant impact on the academic performance of students. (Mhiliwa 2015). It was found that the distance of a school affects the academic performance of students. He emphasized that the longer the distance of a school from a student's residence the more tired and hungry the student becomes, hence, it will negatively affect their academic performance. He argued that students in community schools will continue to perform poorly if community schools are not provided within their community.

Students' factors that affect their academic performance could be classified into internal and social factors. They found that the internal factors that influence students' academic performance included interest in content of a subject, internal satisfaction, and aspiration. (Maric and Sakac 2014). The social factors also included social prestige and material reward corroborated with students level of interest in a subject, influence their academic performance (MeenuDev 2016). It was asserted that student's attitude to school and their interest in learning influence their academic performance. (Kpolovie, Joe, and Okoto 2014). Another type of influence that parents have to their child's

academic performance is their education. Students whose parents finished college level and graduate degrees are over five times more likely to earn college degree themselves compared to those whose parents didn't get past secondary (Carnevale, & Strohl, 2013).

Parental involvement is an individual right and responsibility for families, and a social need. It is generally accepted that without the positive cooperation of family and school, it is not possible to reach the high standards set for educational outcomes by a demanding society. In the study of Levanda it was stated that parental involvement included a wide variety of actions parents take for the benefit of children's academic success at school (Levanda, 2011).

According to statistics PSA (2012), of the 92.1 million household populations in the Philippines, 50.4 percent were males and 49.6 percent were females. This resulted in a sex ratio of 102 males per 100 females. The sex ratio in 2000 was 101 males per 100 females. This was contrary to the present study. In the present study there were more female guardians (195 or 73.58%) than male (70 or 26.52%).

By region, NCR had the highest median age of 25.5 years, with the median age for its male population one year lower than that for female (24.9 years and 26.0 years, respectively). ARMM had the lowest median age of 18.1 years. The median age for its male population was 17.8 years, half a year lower than the median age for its female population (18.3 years), PSA (2012).

In the 2010 Census of Population and Housing (2010 CPH), over, 19.1 percent had finished at most high school, 11.7 percent completed at most elementary education, 10.1 percent were academic degree holders, and 2.7 percent were post-secondary graduates. Among those with college/academic

degrees, females (56.1 percent) outnumbered males (43.9 percent). Similarly, there were more females (58.0 percent) than males (42.0 percent) among those with post baccalaureate courses, Philippine Statistics Authority (2013).

Due to the prevailing problem of the country which is poverty, a substantial number of students do not make the transition from elementary school to high school. The Department of Education (DepEd) data show that for every 100 children who enter Grade 1, close to 15 do not make it into Grade 2, and roughly one-quarter or 24 percent have dropped out before Grade 4 (Luz, 2007). Meanwhile, on December 2013, the NSO Census of Population and Housing (CPH) shows that out of the 71.5 million individuals who are 10 years old and above, 97.5 percent or 69.8 million are literate or could read and write (Selangan, 2015).

According to Sanchez (2019) in 2018, the average monthly salary in the Philippines was about 48.8 thousand Philippine pesos. For 2019, the average monthly wage was forecasted to be about 50.6 thousand Philippine pesos.

Learning at Home

A parent is the child's first and most important teacher in life and he or she is expected to play an active role in the child's preschool journey because it is believed that a parent and child should grow together and have a rewarding preschool experience. This follows subsequently by school life where academic performance is expected to be high. The parent is supposed to be supportive to the child in all aspects which include socially, physically, mentally and also emotionally (Epstein, 2001).

One of the studies said that parental involvement at home can include activities such as discussing about school, helping with homework, and reading with children. Involvement at school may include parents volunteering in the classroom, attending workshops, or attending school plays and sporting events (Rain and William, 2011).

Supporting the above statement, parents are the ones who provide their child's needs dealing with school activities. The other requirement the child needs is playing materials. Parent must provide some of these demonstration and instructional materials for their children.

These materials are important because they help the child to play, to assist in concept building, to promote discovery and creativity and to enhance interaction with others as they play. In this study, parental involvement broadly include activities such as helping with homework, discussing school events or courses, volunteering at school and coming to participate in schools' events. Parental involvement is a function of a parent's beliefs about parental roles and responsibilities. A parent can help the children succeed in school and the opportunities for involvement should be provided by the school or the teacher. The importance of early academic success, a child's academic success, has been found to be relatively stable after early elementary school (Mwirichia, 2013).

Parents must be considered a constant and principle component of curriculum. (Nihat Şad & Gürbüztürk, 2013). They add that success at school is guaranteed if school-based instruction is supported by parents' involvement at home. Involving parents in education has been reported to yield positive outcomes in many aspects including increased student attendance to and satisfaction with school, better academic achievement, motivation, school attachment, responsibility and confidence, better social adaptation and less discipline problems.

If the parents are involved in educating their children, it is tantamount to saying that the school is proactive in implementing changes or development among the students. As parent's involvement is increased, teachers and school administrators also raise the chance to realize quality reform in education (Sapungan, and Sapunga, 2014).

Some school systems have employed parent involvement coordinators to lead and coordinate parental involvement activities and programs within the system in an effort to overcome obstacles between the home and school (Epstein, 2001). Epstein described the role of parent involvement coordinators as a way of encouraging more parents to become involved in a variety of aspects of the school. Parental involvement coordinators often conduct workshops for parents to inform them of the school curriculum and remind them that they are their child's most important teacher (Epstein, 2009). Parental involvement refers to the amount of participation a parent has when it comes to the schooling of his/her children. Some schools foster healthy parental involvement, but sometimes parents have hesitations if they will involve themselves with their children's education. It has been advocated in Western countries. However, there is a body of literature that examines the significance of social and cultural influences and the effects of parents' involvement in and expectations of their children's development and learning. It is important for schools to recognize the existence of cultural variations in parent involvement because there are differences among parents with diverse background on when, why, and how they are involved in their children's education.

Parenting is important in the Philippine society because family is viewed as a center of one's social world. But, social contexts in which Filipino families are embedded have changed rapidly over the past ten years (Ochoa & Torre, n.d.).

Volunteering

To improve the involvement of parents in the education process, several programs were launched by the Philippine's Department of Education such as the "Adopt-A-School-Program" as well as the "Brigada Eskwela" Program which brought together teachers, parents, and community members every 3rd week of May to prepare public schools for opening. The spirit of "Bayanihan" (spirit of kinship and camaraderie) was revived when private organizations in the community contribute in generating resources needed for repairs and upkeep of school facilities.

This is one way of fostering parental involvement since parents are the major stakeholders of every school and should realize their roles in their child's learning development with the help of the teachers of the Department of Education (DepEd, 2008).

"When schools have reputations for being successful, they generally have lots of engagement from parents" (Peters 2012). It was in his qualitative study on Parent Involvement in Public Primary Schools in Kenya that a society needs to increase its level of educational involvement and that starts with the support by the parents. He claims that parent-school linkages can be enhanced through the teacher/parent relationship (Mwai Kimu 2012).

There are varied strategies that the schools can use to get the parents involvement in their children's learning. This could be done through going out to the community, or by encouraging parent's participation by publicizing through traditional means (announcements, flyers) and non-traditional methods which include the use of television, phone calls and sending emails.

The use of only traditional measures could tend to be ineffective in such cases where individual parents rely on non-traditional methods. Some schools do not use sound recruitment strategies that motivated parental involvement in school activities. In the same study schools in the Free State decided to use a raffle to select parents be food handlers. This strategy can work well in situations where the school wants to eliminate discrimination by choosing individuals based on their status in the community or favoritism. (Kwatubana and Makhalemele 2015:317).

Decision Making

School Based Management Approach empowers the school heads, teachers, and other stakeholders including the parents to be part of the decision making process. It yielded a positive result in terms of academic performance of the students, through the increased participation of parents and community in the education of their children (Abulencia 2014). The revised guidelines governing "Parents-Teachers Association" clearly prescribed that both elementary and secondary schools shall organize a Parents-Teachers Association (PTA) for the purpose of providing a forum for the

discussion of issues and their solutions related to the total school program, It also ensured total cooperation of parents in the implementation of such program to emphasize that parents should always be part of decision making for their child's education (DepEd, 2009).

In the City of Manila, being a highly urbanized community, parental involvement remains a crucial factor that could impede better school performance. Hence, this study attempted to explore the effectiveness of the simultaneous undertaking of three interventions to facilitate parental involvement that could enhance student performance.

Collaborating with Community

The benefits of positive, active relationships between families, schools, and the community (not only in the academic outcomes of the children, but also in the family's and school's wellbeing) have, up to now, had plenty of supportive evidence. Nevertheless, experience shows that there are many difficulties involved in making participation a reality. Education regulation acknowledges the importance of family participation at school, but neither implementation methods nor the concept of participation are clearly defined.

Family in the Philippines is perceived as an important part of the society. It has been shaped by the unique history, values, experiences, adaptations, and ways of being that characterize the Filipino people and their culture (Alampay, n.d.). Coupled with the long history of political and social strife, it would seem that Filipino parents face insurmountable challenges in raising their children (Blair, 2014). Filipino parents, in general, subscribe to authoritarian attitudes. Her study reveals that the foregoing cultural values of *kapwa* (helping others), *hiya* (shyness), and *utang na loob* (paying back) are among the interdependent themes that pervade the dynamics of Filipino parenting and parent-child relationships, These are characterized by respect for parental authority and obedience on the part of children, family cohesion, and meeting familial obligations. Alampay (n.d),

In a qualitative study on Parenting in the Philippines, findings show that Filipino parenting behaviors may shift in the years to come. The consequences of these emergent beliefs and behaviors for Filipino families and children's development will need to be fully examined before coming out with policies and framework for Parental Involvement . Although Filipino parents across all social class levels typically regard education as essential to their children's success and are willing to go to great lengths to help their children through school, retention is a major concern in Philippine school, as many students do not continue past their elementary grades (Blair, 2014). In his Comparative study of Filipino and U.S. Parents which uses Questionnaires from six different measures, it concludes that Filipino parents are engaged in their children's education, and want them to succeed, yet the filial responsibilities engrained in their culture necessitates the needs of the family ahead of the needs of the individual child. In his study, it uses theories which envision the flow of family capital. It recommends future studies to attempt to examine more international samples, so as to explore cultural variations, and develop theories which can more readily account for both structural and cultural traits.(Alampay n.d),

Research shows that family-led learning is vital. This involves all the ways that parents support learning through everyday activities, and during the time their children aren't at school. This idea lies at the heart of what is meant by parental engagement. Parental Engagement Building a strong culture of parent-school engagement ,Progressing Parental Engagement Schools benefit significantly through the effect of successful parental engagement on student learning outcomes. Benefits include improved connections with the community, improved school image within the community, and improved family and community satisfaction with the school.

Well targeted and widespread parent and community participation can contribute to school improvement in a number of ways, including:

- Sending clear signals to students about the value of education
- Ensuring school decisions are broadly representative of the school community
- Ensuring school activities and actions are respectful and representative of local cultures
- Building mutual commitment by families to take action in the home that supports learning at school
- Enabling teachers and school leaders to access expertise and perspectives that support curriculum.

Parent-teacher partnership makes tremendous impact on children's education (Llamas and Tuazon 2016). Parents become comfortable when the education system requires their involvement in school activities. The strong collaboration of parents with school authorities can lead to increased improvement in both physical and academic performance of the school. Hence, school administrators have to encourage parents to get involved and make contribution towards helping the school achieve its missions and goals (Sapungan & Sapungan, 2014:45).

As such, behavioral involvement and home supervision magnifies the academic performance of children. (Ma, Shen, Krenn, Hu, & Yuan., 2016; Partin ,2017). Another benefit that was established regarding parental involvement is that

parent teacher partnership is improved, thus, become an integral foundation of academic performance of children as problems arising from academic performance are easily solved by the partnership of parents and the school (Llamas & Tuazon, 2016). This will pave way to a strong collaborative relationship between the school and the parents to improve the learning capabilities of the students and their academic achievement. With their parents involved in their education, children tend to focus more in schoolwork. This primarily motivates them to strive more and not give up easily when they are having a hard time (Sapungan & Sapungan, 2015; Kwatubana & Makhalemele, 2015). On the other hand, there are also negative effects of parental involvement in the academic performance of their children.

Parent-teacher partnership makes tremendous impact on children's education (Llamas and Tuazon 2016). Parents become comfortable when the education system requires their involvement in school activities. The strong collaboration of parents with school authorities can lead to increased improvement in both physical and academic performance of the school. Hence, school administrators have to encourage parents to get involved and make contribution towards helping the school achieve its missions and goals (Sapungan & Sapungan, 2014:45).

Seeing parents involved in the education of their children is a good thing because it improves academic performance. Learners become more focused in their school work (Kwatubana & Makhalemele, 2015:315). Learners whose parents are involved, are active and ready to learn, they learn to be punctual from young age, they learn to be persistent as the parents would be continuously enquiring about their progress and they would not want to disappoint them. Taking responsibility becomes a part of the nature of such children as they plan ahead and are able to do their work according to their schedule, which is the quality of being organized (Sapungan & Sapungan, 2014:45)

Parental involvement is linked to improved behaviour, low levels of absenteeism and optimistic attitudes (Sivertsen 2015). School must learn to build a good relationship with parent (Young Soon Park, 2012). Both parents are responsible in responding to their child's need. It has been observed that often only the mother has the chance to attend the child's need in school. Certain observations even in regular classes reveal that only the mother has the time to talk to teachers for their child's development (Winegardner, 2011).

Failure to sufficiently train pre service teachers is a significant obstacle in promoting parental involvement in the schools (Epstein, 1995). Classes could be incorporated into teacher education programs and advanced degree programs to assist in defining an educator's role in school, family, and community partnerships (Epstein, 1995).

Communicating

Communication is seen as the basic foundation for learning and the means for developing parent involvement programs and building a strong home-school partnership. The guide presents strategies that schools and teachers are using to communicate with parents and suggests ideas and information that parents need to help their children succeed in school. It provides examples of the following categories: (1) partnership pledges; (2) school newsletters; (3) school handbooks; (4) parent surveys and interviews; (5) using the telephone; (6) special meetings; (7) home visits; and (8) communicating through volunteers. The second section is organized to provide ideas on how teachers can improve their working relations with parents. It presents examples of the following categories: (1) introductory and end-of-the-year letters; (2) classroom newsletters; (3) report cards and interim progress reports; (4) homework; (5) home learning activities; (6) parent-teacher conferencing; and (7) telephone reports.

When parents are involved, the students feel that they are supported, and they react more positively and is evident through their academic achievement. Family's emotional support is beneficial to the students, as it not only promotes academic success but also psychological well-being and thus encourages better student engagement in schools (Roksa & Kinsley, 2019). Aside from such support, a parent's influence also helps in shaping the child's predisposition to academics and school related skills. From a very early age, parental habits strongly influence childhood development and their capabilities to learn. Children whose parents have more time to spend helping and guiding their children in school works, developed significant verbal and communication skills (Fernald, 2013). In that same manner, caregivers or parents of children influences cognitive development. (Sperry, Sperry, & Miller, 2018).

Parental involvement can have a positive effect on a student's education. Young students whose parents read to them tend to have better language acquisition, literacy development, later achievement in reading comprehension and higher overall success in school programs that involve parents in their children's education also have been shown to improve students' academic performance. The benefits of parental involvement have been found for students of all ages from all economic, educational, racial and ethnic backgrounds. These could be attained through Parent Teacher Association (PTA). Parent Teacher Association addresses issues that are important to parents and public school administrators. It comprises millions of families, students, teachers, administrators and business and community leaders committed to the educational success of children and the promotion of parental engagement in schools. (Ocampo, 2015).

Parental involvement uses the contextual description which includes communication with teachers about school progress and school visits at home which includes encouragement of children to success, monitoring of homework and attending fieldtrips. (Nyarko, 2011)

Studies show that students with helicopter parents have significantly higher levels of anxiety, depression and less satisfaction with life. This negative effect on the students is largely explained by the perceived violation of the students' need for autonomy, independence and competence. (Schiffman, Liss, Miles-McLean, Geary, Erchull, & Tashner, 2014). With age-appropriate parental involvement, the students feel that they are supported, and the learners react more positively translating through their academic achievement. (Fingerman, Cheng, Wesselmann, Zarit, Furstenberg, & Birditt, 2012). In this regard, family's emotional support is beneficial to the students, as it promotes academic success and psychological well-being. This in turn encourages better student engagement in schools (Roksa & Kinsley, 2019). Children whose parents have more time to spend helping and guiding them in school works, developed significant verbal and communication skills (Fox, Levitt, & Nelson III, 2010; Weisleder, & Fernald, 2013).

Studies also established that caregivers or parents of children influence cognitive development. (Sperry, Sperry, & Miller, 2018). The same way that availability of books at home consistently predicts educational achievement and their test scores in many countries (Wößmann, Ursprung, & Schuetz, 2005). This type of child's environment and available resources is crucial in their academic performance. Students whose parents finished college level and graduate degrees are over five times more likely to earn college degree themselves as they evidently found a relevant model through their parents (Carnevale, & Strohl, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored in the theory of Epstein, et.al. (2009) that the parental involvement is divided into six categories including Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Decision Making, and Collaborating with the Community. The study is delimited on the Parental Involvement as Predictor of Student Academic Performance.

Epstein's Parental Involvement Model according to this theory, affects student achievement because these interactions affect students' motivation, their sense of competence, and the belief that they have control over their success in school. It predicts that children whose parents are involved in their education will be more likely to develop a strong, positive sense of efficacy for successfully. Parental involvement in schools is more than attending homeroom and PTCA meetings. Findings have implications for how Filipino parents and educators can support the academic success of children.

Learners of all groups and levels yield when their supportive parents are implicated in their education. It implies that guardians who are informed and engrossed in their children's trainings can bring sanguinely and impact to their child's attitude and performance. One facet of parent's involvement that has large impact on pupil's achievement is parental expectations. Pupils accomplish more when their parents anticipate more. Learning environment must create an effective partnership by providing an open and communicative milieu with its wider community, bridging the gap between the classroom and the home, and the school and the family.

Epstein's Parent Involvement Model

Epstein (2001), introduced six types of parent involvement: (a.) parenting, (b.) communicating, (c.) volunteering, (d.) learning at home, (e.) decision making and (f.) collaborating with community. This model, through comprehensive and helpful in employment to school programs, is more focused on the perspectives of teachers and its processes.

Most of the types mentioned, can be initiated by teachers – but the main actor is the parent and must be the primary concern if his/ her involvement is to be studied. Parental involvement. Epstein (1983, 1992, & 1994) has suggested a widely recognized typology to account for different levels of parental involvement in their children's education. Epstein identified four types of parental involvement: (a) basic obligations, (b) school-to-home communications, (c) parent involvement at school, and (d) parent involvement in learning at home. Later Epstein expanded the typology and defined six levels (types) of school-related opportunities for parental involvement: (a) assisting parents in child rearing skills, (b) school-parent communication, (c) involving parents in school volunteer opportunities, (d) including parents in home-based learning, (e) involving parents in school decision making, and (f) involving parents in school-community collaborations. These issues are viewed by Epstein from the perspectives of schools and is concerned primarily with what schools (teachers) can do to stimulate more active parental involvement.

Epstein's Framework of Parental Involvement

Figure 1
Epstein's Model for Parental Involvement

Parenting- Assists families with parenting skills, family support, understanding child and adolescent development, and setting home conditions to support learning at each age and grade level. Assist schools in understanding families' backgrounds, cultures, and goals for children.

Communicating-Communicates with families about school programs and student progress. Create two-way communication channels between school and home.

Volunteering –Improves recruitment, training, activities, and schedules to involve families as volunteers and as audiences at the school or in other locations. Enable educators to work with volunteers who support students and the school.

Learning at Home- Involves families with their children in academic learning at home, including homework, goal setting, and other curriculum-related activities, encourages teachers to design homework that enables students to share and discuss interesting tasks.

Decision-Making-Includes families as participants in school decisions, governance, and advocacy activities through school councils or improvement teams, committees, and parent organizations.

Collaborating with the Community-Coordinate resources and services for families, students, and the school with community groups, including businesses, agencies, cultural and civic organizations, and colleges or universities. Enable all to contribute service to the community.

Type of parental engagement	Examples of parental engagement strategies
<p>Volunteering Strategies that organize and support family and community members in their efforts</p>	<p>Annual survey (or other inclusive method) to identify interests, talents, and availability of volunteers Develop a database of parent and community skills, talents and availability to draw on when required Assess the volunteer needs of the school and list the many ways parents and families can participate and interact with school and the school community Appoint class-parent representatives who can become a welcoming informal network of support Provide a parent room or family space for volunteer work, meetings, and resources for families Conduct a regular review of schedules for students’ performances, games, and assemblies to encourage all families to attend as daytime and evening audiences Issue invitations for parent participation that are personal and specific, rather than general</p>
<p>Learning at home Strategies that assist families to boost home-learning conditions to support student academic achievement by involving families with their children on homework and other curriculum related activities and decisions.</p> <p>Parenting Help all families establish home environments to support children as students.</p>	<p>Information for families on required skills in all subjects at each year level Information on homework policies and how to monitor and discuss schoolwork at home Information on how to assist students with skills that they need to improve Regular schedule of interactive homework that requires students to demonstrate and discuss what they are learning in class Arrange for folders of student work to be sent home regularly for review and comment Calendars with daily or weekly activities for parents and students to do at home or in the community.</p> <p>Parent education and other courses or training for parents(e.g. , family literacy) Family support programs to assist families with health, nutrition and other services.</p>
<p>Communicating Establish clear two – way channels for communications from home to school and from school to home</p> <p>Decision Making Strategies that include families and community members as partners in school decisions and develop parent leaders and representatives.</p>	<p>Conferences with every parent , with follow-ups as needed. Regular schedule of useful notices , memos, phone calls , newsletters, and other communications.</p> <p>Arrange for the school community to be consulted on new school policies, e.g. assessment, reporting and curriculum changes Encourage active participation in the formal parents’ organisation in the school council and/or P&C, advisory councils, or committees for parent leadership and participation Establish networks to link all families with parent representatives Offer training and support to parent leaders.</p>

<p>Collaborating with Community Strategies that coordinate resources and services from the community to strengthen school programs, family practices, and student learning and development.</p>	<p>Involve family or community representatives in small group discussions about the role each group or person can play in ensuring the success of every child Build strong connections between schools and community organisations. For example, invite local service groups to become involved with the school in a variety of ways, such as mentoring students and speaking to classes Create connections with local health and welfare services to facilitate access to such support for the school community Integrate school partnerships with cultural groups, government and nongovernment agencies to support activities, e.g. play group, breakfast clubs Encourage community use of school facilities, e.g. community rooms, library, halls and gyms.</p>
---	---

Research Questions

This study examined the relationship between parental involvement and academic performance of Grade 7 students in Marikina High School. It seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of parents in terms of gender, age, educational attainment and socio economic status?
2. What are the Academic Performances of Grade 7 students?
3. What is the level of Parental Involvement in terms of Epstein’s six types of Parental Involvement?
4. What is the relationship of the level of Parental Involvement and Academic Performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the levels of parental involvement when parents are grouped according to their profile variables? at home and at school.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between the parents’ involvement and academic performance of the Grade 7 students in Marikina High School for the SY: 2019- 2020. (mam buri)
2. There is no significant relationship between the profile of respondents and parental involvement.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are operationally defined .

Academic Performance –This refers to student’s grades based on recitation, quizzes and projects he/ she performed in school. In this study, the second grading general weighted average is considered.

Adolescence .This refers to the learners between 13 to 17 years of age.

Home involvement. This refers to the involvement of parents at home including s activities such as discussions about school work, helping with homework, and reading with children.

Home- School Collaboration. This refers to Grade 7 family and community as partners together to support students education or academic performances.

Parental Involvement . This refers to the participation of the Grade 7 parents such as a meaningful communication involving student academic learning, other school activities and character development.

Parenting styles. This refers to the type and amount of action taken by the parents.

Pupils- This refers to Grade 7 students of Marikina High School.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on adolescents who are currently Grade 7 students of Marikina High School and targeted their parents or guardian. The research also focused on the amount of parental involvement , its aspects and its effects to the academic performance of the learners. The students’ academic performance in the school is reflected in their grades on their report card and were secured from the records. Students whose guardians are relatives and the ones

taking care of them are excluded from this study.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive correlational research design was used for this study. The aim of this study is to answer the emerging questions about the relationship of parental involvement and academic performance of Grade 7 students in the local context. Since there are a few local studies that focus on the nuances of parental involvement and academic performance, a growing assumption from the parents holds the belief that it was the school and the teacher's sole duty to make their children succeed academically. They believe that parental involvement does not affect the academic performance of the learners. This study aims to look at that nuance and also, explore if there is any specific aspects of parental involvement that help students perform well in school. A descriptive relational research design is employed to investigate the connection between parental involvement and school performance. With that established, it is imperative to also look for any barrier that hinders the academic performance of learners with regards to parental involvement. Upon the establishment of a comprehensible data, the School Guidance Office can start to design, to develop and to implement a relevant intervention plan as a part of a research based practice.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Marikina High School, located at F. Torres, Concepcion 1 Marikina City. The School has an estimated population of 3204 students ages from 13- 18 . It includes Grade 7 level which has male and female students total of 769; Grade 8 level has male and female students with the total of 817; Grade 9 level has male and female students with the total of total of 879 and for the Grade 10 level it has male and female students with a total of 739 and the teachers ages 21-64 are composed of male 24 and female 115 total of 139. School staff and administrators, under the leadership of Principal Lauro Z. de Guzman have served the school for the last five years. [The School has seen a wide range of parental behavior for the last decade, and what was noteworthy was that, most parents were either too busy to engage the school or that they deliberately uninvolve themselves with the educational concerns of their children.

Despite of this, parents who were involved with the schools are the parents of those who were performing quite adequately and well in school.]

Participants of the Study

Grade 7 students of Marikina High School and their parents were the participants of this study. The student participants' age range from 12 to 13 years of age, while their parents' age ranged from 30 to 60 years of age. The population had a total of 769 students consist of 388 male and 381 female in the school year 2019-2020 . A sample of 265 students were used. The researcher made use of Cluster Sampling to get the number of student participants.

The Grade 7 level had 20 sections . There was an average class size of forty (40) students per sections. The researcher utilized 7 sections namely: 7- kadakilaan, 7- kapuri-puri , 7- Kahusayan , 7- Kagitingan, 7- kasipagan , 7- katapatan and 7- kawanggawa .Permission to conduct data gathering procedure was obtained from the Division Office of Marikina, along with the informed consent of the parents whose children were participants in the study. The questionnaire was modified by Family Involvement Questionnaire and it was validated by the Professional experts.

Research Instruments

This study used an instrument adapted and modified from the Parent and School Survey (Ringenberg, Funk, Mullen, Wilford, & Kramer, 2005) which was based on Epstein's framework, which underwent expert content validation with Filipino translation for each item. The data needed for the academic performance of the students were gathered from the department part of the report card of Grade 7 students of the second grading period during school year 2019-2020. To gather the level of Parental Involvement of parents , a checklist was made. It asked for the parental involvement at home and parental involvement at school. It consisted of 20 items in which the parents indicated how often they did the parental involvement with their children as evaluated by using the following rating :

- 4- Always
- 3- Frequently
- 2- Sometimes
- 1- Never

Before administering the aforementioned questionnaire and inventory actual respondents, it was tried out first to twenty (20) parents of Grade 7 students who were not members of the sample , for the purpose of modification and improvement of the items.

In determining the students 'academic performance, general weighted average for the second grading period of each student of the sample was extracted and tallied.

Data Collection

Upon obtaining the necessary permits and informing consent from parents, data gathering phase of the study commenced. With participating parents' consent, the researcher administered the Family Involvement Questionnaires to the participating parents, an instrument designed to measure parental involvement in their child's education based on Eipstein framework. The participating student's academic performance was measured by obtaining their general weighted average at the end of the second grading period .

The Family Involvement Questionnaires results were tallied in Microsoft Excel, coded as follows: 4- Always, 3- Frequently, 2- Sometimes, 1- Never. To obtain global scores representing parental involvement, mean scores were obtained with higher score, meaning more involvement on part of the parents to their child's education. Next, the data collected and encoded was participating students's general weighted average at the end of the 2nd grading period. Upon completion of the parental involvement mean scores and the students general weighted average, they were encoded to IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. The scores correlated to test if there was relationship between the two variables.

Treatment of Data

The data that were gathered to answer the specific problems of this study were subjected to statistical treatment.

The data in Problem number 1 :What is the profile of parent in gender, age, educational attainment and socio economic status? This was treated with the use of Frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents based on the different profiles considered.

To Determine the answer in Problem number 2 - What is the Academic Performance of Grade 7 students? The data was treated with the use of Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation.

The data in Problem number 3 - What is the level of Parental Involvement in terms of Epstein's six types of Parental Involvement? The data was treated by the use of weighted mean .

For Problem Number 4 - Is there a significant relationship between the Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of the students? The data was subjected to Chi square test.

To treat the Data in Problem number 5 - Is there a significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and when parents are grouped according to their profile variables at home and at school – Chi square test was used.

RESULTS

Problem 1: Profile of the parents in terms of:

- 1.1 Gender;
- 1.2 Age;
- 1.3 Educational attainment; and
- 1.4 Socio-economic Status

Table 1.1
Frequency Distribution of the Parents in Terms of Gender

GENDER	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	70	26.42
Female	195	73.58
Total (N)	265	100.00

Table 1.2
Frequency Distribution of the Parents in Terms of Age

AGE	Frquency (f)	Percentage (%)
30-35	72	21.17
36-40	74	27.92
41-45	46	17.36
46-50	57	21.51
51& above	16	6.04
Total (N)	265	100.00

Table 1.3
Frequency Distribution of the Parents in Terms of Educational Attainment

EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
MA Graduate	9	3.41
College	27	10.19
Vocational	33	12.45
High School	186	70.19
Elementary	10	3.77
Total (N)	265	100.00

Table 1.4
Frequency Distribution of the Parents in Terms of Socio-economic Status

FAMILY INCOME	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
21,000 and above	45	16.98
16,000-20,999	57	21.50
11,000-15,999	59	22.26
6,000-10,999	51	19.20
5,999 and below	53	20.00
Total (N)	265	100.00

Problem 2. The Academic Performances of Grade 7 Students

The results were entered in Table 2. The adjectival grades are shown below:

Numeric grade range	Adjectival Grade
90-94	Very Satisfactory (VS)
85-89	Satisfactory (S)
80-84	Moderately Satisfactory (MS)
75-79	Unsatisfactory (U)

Table 2
Academic Performance of the Grade 7 Students

GRADES	Frequency	Percentage
Very Satisfactory (90-94)	45	14.90
Satisfactory (85-89)	65	21.53
Moderately Satisfactory (80-84)	62	20.52
Unsatisfactory (75-79)	93	28.12

TOTAL	265	100.00
MEAN	83.17	
Standard Deviation	5.52	

Problem 3. Level of Parental Involvement in terms of Epstein’s six types of Parental Involvement.

Table 3 shows the computed weighted mean and its corresponding verbal interpretation using the 4- Point Likert scale below.

Scale	Verbal Interpretation
4	Always involved (AI)
3	Frequently involved (FI)
2	Sometimes involved (SI)
1	Never involved (NI)

To describe the level of the involvement of parents on the education of their children the following 4 Point Grade scale was used:

Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
3.50- 4.00	High (H)
2.50- 3.49	Moderately High (MH)
1.50- 2.49	Moderately Low (ML)
1.00- 1.49	Low (L)

Table 3.1.
Level of Involvement of Parents at Home

CATEGORIES	Level of Involvement						
Parenting							
3. I spend time with my child every day to follow up on his/her lesson. (Naglalaanngorasaraw-araw, saakinganakupanggabayansakanyangmgaleksyon.)	119	7	5	4	3.14	I	H
5. I get a tutor for my child. (Kumukuhaakongtagapagturoparasaakinganak.)	36	6	2	31	1.88	I	L
6. I provide my child’s school materials needed. (Binibigaykoangpangangailanganngakinganakparasakanya ngpag-aaral.)	139	4	5	7	3.23	I	H
8. I prepare nutritional food for my child. (Naghahandangmgamasustansyangpagkainparasaakinganak.)	100	6	1	8	2.86	I	H
10. I regulate my child television viewing and game time. (Nililimitahankoangorassapanonoodngmgaprogramasatele bisyon at paglalaro.)	44	6	1	4	2.26	I	L
Composite Mean	2.674					I	H

Learning at Home							
1. I check the assignment of my child. (Inaalangkung may takdang-aralinangakinganak.)	33	59	52	1	3.15	I	H
2. I help my child in doing his/her project. . (Tinutulunganangakinganakakanyangtakdangaralin.)	47	82	100	6	2.53	I	H
4. I help my child in establishing good habits. (Tinutulunganmagkaroonngmagandangkagawiansapag-aaralangakinganak.)	119	70	42	4	3.03	I	H
Composite Mean	2.90					I	H
Decision Making							
10. I regulate my child television viewing and game time. (Nililimitahankoangorassapanonoodngmgaprogramasatele bisyon at paglalaro.	44	56	91	74	2.26	I	L
Communicating							
7. I send letter to the teacher if there is problem/ urgent matter at home. (Nagbibigayngsulatsagurongakinganakapag may problema.)	111	55	58	41	2.89	I	H
Overall Weighted Mean	2.681					I	H

Table 3.2.
Level of Involvement of Parents at School

CATEGORIES	Level of Involvement						
Parenting							
5. I support my child co-curricular activities such as sports in school. (SinusoportahankoangakinganaksaLarongPampalakasansa kayangeskwelehan).	112	49	75	29	2.92	I	H

7. I accompany my child in going to school. (Hinahatid at sinusundo ang ating anak sa kanyang paaralan.)	89	55	92	29	2.77	I	H
Composite Mean					2.90	I	H
Volunteering							
2. I volunteer in school activities, such as "Brigada Eskwela". (Nakikibahag sa mga gawain o programang pang paaralankatulan ng Brigada Eskwela.)	109	63	69	24	2.97	I	H
9. I volunteer to become one of the classroom aides. (Nagboboluntaryong maging bahagi o katuwang sagawaing pang paaralan.)	118	95	44	8	3.22	I	H
Composite Mean					3.095	I	H
Collaborating							
4. I attend family day activities. (Dumadalos sa mga aktibidad ng paaralantulan ng <i>Family Day</i>)	6	0	0	9	2.88	I	H
6. I allow my child to join in "Field trips." or Educational Tour. (Pinapayag ang ating anak na sumamasalakbay-Aral.)	113	31	74	47	2.79	I	H
Composite Mean					2.835	I	H
Decision Making							
10. I get most of information, about my child's progress from report cards. (Kinukuha ang <i>card</i> ng ating anak tuwing kailangan.)	167	32	4	2	26	I	H
Communicating							
1. I communicate with my child's teacher to follow up his/ her class performance. (Nakikipag- ugnayan sa gurong ating anak pang malaman ang kaganapan sa paaralan.)	161	5	0	9	.39	I	H
3. I attend school meetings and PTA meeting. (Dumadalos sa mga pulong sa eskwelahan.)	49	1	1	4	.23	I	H

10. I get most of information, about my child's progress from report cards. (Kinukuhaangcard ngakinganaktuwingkailangan.)	67	2	4	2	.26	I	H
Composite Mean	3.29					I	H
Overall Weighted Mean	3.076					I	H

Problem 4. Relationship between the level of parental involvement and academic performance of the students.

*Table 4.1.
 Relationship Between Academic Performance and Level of Parental Involvement at Home*

4.1.1. Parenting									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	OF	EF	F	EF	F	EF	
VS (90-94)	3	14.94	2	9.85	0	10.87	0	.34	5
S (85-89)	3	21.58	24	14.23	4	15.7	4	3.49	65
MS (80-84)	3	20.59	18	13.57	8	14.97	3	2.87	62
U (75-79)	9	30.88	14	20.35	2	22.46	8	9.3	93
Total	8		58		4		5		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	48.31								
Decision	Reject H ₀ – Significant Relationship								

4.1.2 Learning at Home									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	F	EF	
VS (90-94)	0	16.98	8	11.89	15	11.04	2	.09	45
S (85-89)	7	24.53	20	17.17	14	15.94	4	7.36	65
MS (80-84)	8	23.4	23	16.38	18	15.21	3	7.02	62

U (75-79)	5	35.09	19	24.57	18	22.81	1	10.5	93
Total	00		70		65		0		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	27.11								
Decision	Reject the Null Hypothesis – Significant Relationship								

4.1.3 Decision Making									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	
VS (90-94)	3	7.47	9	9.51	21	15.45	12	12.6	45
S (85-89)	2	10.79	15	13.74	11	22.32	17	18.2	65
MS (80-84)	9	10.29	7	13.1	16	21,29	24	17.3	62
U (75-79)	0	15.44	25	19.65	43	31.94	21	26	93
Total	4		56		91		74		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	37.35								
Decision	Reject the Null Hypothesis – Significant Relationship								

4.1.4 Communicating									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	F	EF	F	EF	F	EF	
VS (90-94)	6	18.85	0	.34	4	9.85	5	6.96	45
S (85-89)	3	27.226	5	13.49	1	14.23	6	10.1	65
MS (80-84)	0	25.97	7	12.87	7	13.57	8	9.59	62
U (75-79)	2	38.95	3	19.3	6	20.35	2	14.4	93
Total	11		5		8		1		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	34.42								
Decision	Reject the Null Hypothesis - Significant Relationship								

Table 4.2.
Relationship Between Academic Performance and Level of Parental Involvement at School

4.2.1. Parenting									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	F	F	F	EF	OF	EF	
VS (90-94)	3	17.15	9	.83	6	14.09		4.92	45
S (85-89)	5	24.77	5	2.75	0	20.35	5	7.11	65
MS (80-84)	9	23.63	0	2.16	1	19.41	2	6.78	62
U (75-79)	4	35.44	8	8.24	6	29.12	15	10.17	93
Total	01		2		3		29		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	31.30								
Decision	Reject H ₀ - Significant Relationship								

4.2.2. Volunteering									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	F	EF	F	EF	F	F	
VS (90-94)	8	19.18	3	13.41	9	9.67	5	5	45
S (85-89)	1	27.78	1	19.39	7	13.98	6	5	65
MS (80-84)	5	26.43	3	18.48	4	13.33	0	2	62
U (75-79)	9	39.65	2	27.72	7	20.00	5	3	93
Total	13		9		7			49	265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	15.78								
Decision	Accept H ₀ - No Significant Relationship								

4.2.3. Collaborating									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	F	EF	F	EF	OF	EF	
VS (90-94)	7	17.66	6	8.66	9	12.22	13	6.45	45
S (85-89)	5	25.50	3	12.50	8	17.66	9	9.32	65
MS (80-84)	8	24.33	1	11.93	3	16.84	0	8.89	62
U (75-79)	4	36.49	1	17.89	2	25.26	16	13.33	93
Total	04		1		2		38		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	28.59								
Decision	Reject H ₀ - Significant Relationship								

4.2.4. Decision Making									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	
VS (90-94)	8	28.35	0	5.43	7	5.77	10	5.43	45
S (85-89)	3	40.96	4	7.84	14	8.33	14	7.84	65
MS (80-84)	42	39.07	7	7.48	5	7.95	8	7.48	62
U (75-79)	64	58.60	21	11.25	8	11.93	0	11.23	93
Total	167		32		34		32		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	34.68								
Decision	Reject H ₀ - Significant Relationship								

4.2.5. Communicating									
Academic Performance	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	
VS (90-94)	16	27.00	12	7.81	5	6.45	12	3.74	45
S (85-89)	39	39.00	15	11.28	9	9.32	2	5.39	65
MS (80-84)	43	37.20	11	10.76	7	8.89	1	5.14	62

U (75-79)	61	55.80	8	16.14	17	13.33	7	7.72	93
Total	159		46		38		22		265
Critical Value	16.92								
Chi-Square	33.35								
Decision	Reject H ₀ - Significant Relationship								

Problem 5. The Relationship between the parents' level of involvement with regards to profile variables:
5.1 At Home; and
5.2 At School.

Table 5.1.1
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at Home and Gender

Gender	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	F	EF	F	EF	F	EF	F	EF	
Male	0	23.51	8	16.11	3	17.70	7	12.68	70
Female	95	65.49	3	44.89	4	19.10	1	35.32	195
Total	89		61		67		48		265
Critical Value	7.815								
Computed Chi-Square	7.23								
Decision	Accept the H ₀ = No Significant Relationship								

Table 5.1.2
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at Home and Age

Age	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	OF	EF	F	EF	OF	EF	OF	F	
31-35	23	24.18	13	16.57	22	18.2	14	3.04	72
36-40	31	24	21	17.03	19	18.71	3	3.40	74
41-45	12	85	16	10.59	9	11.63	9	.33	46
46-50	21	15.45	6	13.12	11	14.41	19	0.32	57
51 and Above	2	19.17	5	2.30	6	2.53	3	.81	16
Total	89		61		67		48		265
Critical Value	21.03								

Computed Chi-Square	38.14
Decision	Reject the H_0 = Significant Relationship

Table 5.1.3
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at Home and Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	OF	EF	OF	EF	F	EF	OF	EF	
MA	3	3.82	2	2.07	2	2.28	2	1.63	72
College	10	9.07	7	6.22	2	6.83	8	4.89	74
Vocational	16	11.08	12	7.60	4	8.34	1	5.98	46
High School	57	62.47	37	42.82	5	42.03	37	33.69	57
Elementary	3	3.36	3	2.30	4	2.53	0	1.81	16
Total	89		61		67		48		265
Critical Value	21.03								
Computed Chi-Square	45.24								
Decision	Reject the H_0 = Significant Relationship								

Table 5.1.4
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at Home and Socio- Economic Status

Family Income	Level of Involvement at Home								Total
	4 (High)		4 (High)		4 (High)		4 (High)		
	OF	EF	F	EF	F	EF	F	EF	
21,000 and Above	11	15.11	16	10.36	8	11.38	0	8.15	72
16,000-20,999	16	19.14	14	13.12	12	14.41	15	10.32	74
11,000-15,999	23	19.82	12	13.5	15	14.92	9	10.69	46
6,000-10,999	19	17.13	9	11	16	12.89	7	9.24	57
5,999 and Below	20	17.80	10	74	16	13.40	7	9.68	16
Total	89		61		67		48		265
Critical Value	21.03								
Computed Chi-Square	14.85								
Decision	Accept the H_0 = No Significant Relationship								

Table 5.2.1
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at School and Gender

Gender	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
Male									70
Female									195
Total	128		54		57		26		265
Critical Value	7.815								
Computed Chi-Square	18.49								
Decision	Reject the H ₀ = Significant Relationship								

Table 5.2.2
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at School and Age

Age	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	OF	EF	OF	EF	F	EF	F	EF	
31-35	33	34.78	11	14.69	1	15.49		7.06	72
36-40	44	34.74	15	15.08	0	15.92	5	7.26	74
41-45	17	22.22	12	9.37	5	9.89	2	4.51	46
46-50	32	27.53	16	11.62	6	12.26	3	5.59	57
51 and Above		7.73	0	3.26		3.44	9	1.57	16
Total	128		54		57		26		265
Critical Value	21.03								
Computed Chi-Square	41.98								
Decision	Reject the H ₀ = Significant Relationship								

Table 5.2.3
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at School and Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	
MA	4	4.35	2	1.83	0	1.94	3	0.88	9
College	5	13.04	8	5.50	7	5.81	7	2.65	27
Vocational	16	15.94	13	6.72	4	7.10	0	3.24	33

High School	101	89.04	28	37.90	3	40.01	4	18.25	186
Elementary		4.83		2.04		2.15		0.98	10
Total	128		54		57		26		265
Critical Value	21.03								
Computed Chi-Square	39.51								
Decision	Reject the H_0 = Significant Relationship								

Table 5.2.4
Relationship Between the Parent Respondents' Level of Involvement at School and Socio- Economic Status

Family Income	Level of Involvement at School								Total
	4 (High)		3 (Moderately High)		2 (Moderately Low)		1 (Low)		
	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	OF	EF	
21,000 and Above	21	21.74	13	9.17		9.68	5	4.45	72
16,000-20,999	25	27.53	8	11.62	21	12.26	3	5.59	74
11,000-15,999	28	28.5	12	12.02	8	12.69	11	5.79	46
6,000-10,999	19	24.63	13	10.39	14	10.97	5	5	57
5,999 and Below	35	25.60	8	10.88		5.20		5.24	16
Total	128		54		57		26		265
Critical Value	21.03								
Computed Chi-Square	27.42								
Decision	Reject the H_0 = Significant Relationship								

DISCUSSION

This study entitled “Parental Involvement and Academic Performance of Grade 7 Students in Marikina High School” aimed to determine the relationship of parental involvement to the academic performance of Grade 7 student in Marikina High School during the school year 2019-2020. The profile variables of the parents were also considered and correlated with the level of parental involvement.

Specifically, the researcher attempts to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of parent in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. gender;
 - 1.2. age;
 - 1.3. educational attainment; and
 - 1.4. socio-economic status?
2. What is the academic performance of Grade 7 students?
3. What is the level of Parental Involvement in terms of Epstein’s six types of parental involvement:
 - 3.1. at home; and
 - 3.2. at school?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and academic performance of the students?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and when parents are grouped

according to their profile variables?

This study made use of descriptive correlational method in determining the relationship between the level of parental involvement and academic performance of the students and the profile variables of the parents as well. The respondents of the study were the 265 students and parents of the Grade 7 students of Marikina High School during the school year 2019-2020. The study adapted the 20 item Family Involvement Questionnaires that focused on the parental involvement at home and at school. The data gathered were subjected to statistical treatment using frequency distribution, percentage, weighted mean, and chi-square test.

Based on the data gathered from the use of the standardized questionnaire and the grades of the students, the following are the summary of the findings of the study:

1. Of the total 265 parent respondents 195 or 73.58% were female and 70 or 26.42% were male. Fifty one percent or 146 parents had ages in the range of 30-40 and about 6.04% or 16 were in the oldest age range of 51 and above. In terms of educational attainment parents who finished high school had the largest frequency of 186 or 70.19% while only 10 or 3.77 finished elementary the rest were able to get higher level of education. The income of most parents which is 59 or 22.26% was in the range of 11,000 to 15,000 while the smallest frequency of 45 parents had income in the range of 21,000 and above.
2. The highest frequency was in the score range of 75-79 with 93 students or 28.12% getting the said grade and the lowest number of students which was 45 had grades in the highest range of 90-94. The mean score of the students was 83.117 with the standard deviation of 5.52 indicating how the grades of the students were scattered.
3. The level of involvements of parents in their children's education at home in terms of parenting, learning at home, decision making, communicating were 2.674, 2.90, 2.26, and 2.89 respectively. Their weighted means indicated that the parents were frequently involved in the education of their children except for decision making where the parents agreed that they sometimes participated in the decision about school matters at home. The overall weighted mean of 2.681 on the level of involvement of parents at home implied that they had moderately high level of involvement at home with regards to their children's education. In terms of involvement of parents at school the overall weighted mean was 3.076 indicating that the parents had moderately high level of parental involvement at school as a result of the individual weighted means for each category as 2.90 for parenting; 3.095 for volunteering; 2.835 for collaborating; 3.26 for decision making and 3.29 for communicating.
4. A significant relationship existed between the academic performance of their children and the level of involvements of parents with the education of their children at home and in terms of parenting, learning at home, decision making and communicating as revealed by their computed chi-square values of 48.31, 27.11, 37.35, and 34.42 respectively as compared to the critical value of 16.92. Similarly, the academic performance of the students were significantly correlated with level of parental involvement at school in terms of parenting, collaborating, decision making, and communicating as disclosed by their high weighted means of 31.30, 28.59, 34.68 and 33.35
5. against the critical value of 16.92. On the other hand, no significant relationship resulted between the academic performance of students and the level of involvement of parents at school in terms of volunteering as the computed chi-square value of 15.78 was lower than the critical value of 16.92.
6. The age and educational attainment of parents were significantly correlated with the level of involvements of parents in the education of their children at home since the computed chi-square value of 38.14 and 45.24 exceeded the critical value of 21.03. On the contrary, the gender and socio-economic status of the parents were not significantly correlated with the level of parental involvement at home on account of lower computed chi-square values of 7.23 and 14.85 as compared to critical values of 7.815 and 21.03 respectively. For the level of involvement of parents at school a significant correlation in all profile variables considered were evident as the computed chi-square values of 18.49 for gender, 41.98 for age, 39.51 for educational attainment and 27.42 for socio-economic status exceeded the critical values of 7.815 for gender and 21.03 for all the other variables.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The parent-respondents were mostly female, middle-aged, graduate of high school and above and with monthly income all below the average monthly salary declared by Sanchez (2019).
2. The Grade 7 students considered in this study were performing moderately satisfactory in their class.
3. The parent respondents had moderately high level of involvements in their children's educational concerns both at home and school.
4. The moderately satisfactory grades of the Grade 7 students could be attributed to the moderately high level of involvement of parents in the education of their children at home and at school.
5. Middle-aged parents with higher educational attainment contributed to the high level of parental involvements at home. The gender of the parents and monthly income does not contribute to the high level of parental involvement at home. On the other hand female, middle-aged parents with high educational attainment and

greater monthly income contributed to the high level of involvement of parents in the education of their children at school.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the following recommendations were drawn after the undertaking of the study:

1. Since no significant relationship resulted from the correlation between the level of parental involvement in school in terms of volunteering and academic performance the school might consider coming up with activities, projects or programs that will entice the parents to volunteer to be part of the said activity/project or program.
2. A replication of the study can be conducted using students at risk to find out the extent of parental involvement with such group of students and how this correlate to their academic performance.
3. A qualitative study to determine involvement activities that attract parents to participate in their children's schools and also to determine the most meaningful and useful activities based on parents' perceptions is recommended for further study.
4. This study employed the use of descriptive research methodology which might not produce all of the related functions of the principles, extent of use and effectiveness of the selected principles, methods, techniques and tools. It is, therefore, recommended that similar studies be conducted with a variety of research methodology to identify the changing perceptions on parental involvement, such as employing the use of two groups the control and experimental group.
5. The potential of new formats and media should be explored to support parental involvement specifically in the kindergarten or primary level. Today's youngsters were born in the age of the Internet. Many are more technologically savvy than the parents. To connect with these kids, parents must learn to speak their language and become conversant with the technology that comes so naturally to the young. However, if they are to succeed with it, they need a deep understanding of the tools available, as well as meaningful reflection about how to use them to enhance communication with the children. The school should consider conducting seminar-workshop for the parents on the use of technology and online spaces/resources.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Alampay, L. P. (2014). Parenting in the Philippines. In *Parenting across cultures* (pp. 105-121). Springer, Dordrecht.
- [2]. Abulencia A. F. (2014). Modeling the relations among parental involvement, school engagement and academic performance of high school students. *International Education Studies*, 7(4), 47-56.
- [3]. Bernardo, A. B. (2010). Exploring Filipino adolescents' perceptions of the legitimacy of parental authority over academic behaviors. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 31(4), 273-280.
- [4]. Blair, S. L. (2014). Parental involvement and children's educational performance: A comparison of Filipino and US parents. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 45(3), 351-366.
- [5]. Castro, M., Expósito-Casas, E., López-Martín, E., Lizasoain, L., Navarro-Asencio, E., & Gaviria, J. L. (2015). Parental involvement on student academic achievement: A meta-analysis. *Educational research review*, 14, 33-46.
- [6]. Carnevale, A. P., & Strohl, J. (2013). Separate & Unequal How Higher Education Reinforces the Intergenerational Reproduction of White Racial Privilege.
- [7]. Clinton, J., & Hattie, J. (2013). New Zealand students' perceptions of parental involvement in learning and schooling. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education*, 33(3), 324-337.
- [8]. Department of Education. Retrieved from <http://www.deped.gov.ph/memos>.
- [9]. Epstein, J. L. (2001). *School, family, and community partnerships: Preparing educators and improving schools*. Boulder, CO: Westview.
- [10]. Fingerman, K. L., Cheng, Y. P., Wesselmann, E. D., Zarit, S., Furstenberg, F., & Birditt, K. S. (2012). Helicopter parents and landing pad kids: Intense parental support of grown children. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 74(4), 880-896.
- [11]. Henderson, A. T., & Berla, N. (1994). *A new generation of evidence: The family is critical to student achievement*.
- [12]. Kimaro, A. R., & Machumu, H. J. (2015). Impacts of parental involvement in school activities on academic achievement of primary school children. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(8), 483-494.
- [13]. Khajehpour, M. (2011). Relationship between emotional intelligence, parental involvement and academic performance of high school students. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15, 1081-1086.
- [14]. Khajehpour, M., & Ghazvini, S. D. (2011). The role of parental involvement affect in children's academic performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 15, 1204-1208.
- [15]. Kwatubana, S., & Makhalemele, T. (2015). Parental Involvement in the Process of Implementation of the National School Nutrition Programme in Public Schools. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 9(3), 315-323.

- [16]. Llamas, A.V. & Tuazon, A. P. (2016). School practices in parental involvement, its expected results and barriers in public secondary schools. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*, 6(1):69-78
- [17]. Ma, X., Shen, J., Krenn, H. Y., Hu, S., & Yuan, J. (2016). A meta-analysis of the relationship between learning outcomes and parental involvement during early childhood education and early elementary education. *Educational Psychology Review*, 28(4), 771-801.
- [18]. Marshall, I. A., & Jackman, G. A. (2015). Parental Involvement, Student Active Engagement and the "Secondary Slump" Phenomenon--Evidence from a Three-Year Study in a Barbadian Secondary School. *International Education Studies*, 8(7), 84-96.
- [19]. Partin, D. (2017). *THE EFFECT OF PARENTAL VALUATION OF EDUCATION ON STUDENT ACHIEVEMENT* (Doctoral dissertation, Carson-Newman University).
- [20]. Perez, M. (2018). Educators' perspectives on school family involvement within the context of a PAT structure: A qualitative case study.
- [21]. Porumbu, D., & Necşoi, D. V. (2013). Relationship between parental involvement/attitude and children's school achievements. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 76, 706-710.
- [22]. Rafiq, H. M. W., Fatima, T., Sohail, M. M., Saleem, M., & Khan, M. A. (2013). Parental involvement and academic achievement: A study on secondary school students of Lahore, Pakistan. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(8), 209-223.
- [23]. Ringenberg, M., Funk, V., Mullen, K., Wilford, A., Kramer, J. (2005). Test-Retest Reliability of the Parent And School Survey (PASS). Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ794812.pdf>
- [24]. Roksa, J., & Kinsley, P. (2019). The role of family support in facilitating academic success of low-income students. *Research in Higher Education*, 60(4), 415-436.
- [25]. Sapungan, G. M., & Sapungan, R. M. (2014). Parental involvement in child's education: Importance, barriers and benefits. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education*, 3(2), 23-43.
- [26]. Schiffrin, H. H., Liss, M., Miles-McLean, H., Geary, K. A., Erchull, M. J., & Tashner, T. (2014). Helping or hovering? The effects of helicopter parenting on college students' well-being. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 23(3), 548-557.
- [27]. Selangan. (2015). The Reading Profile of Children in the Philippines. Literacy and World Languages Article. Retrieved from <http://www.edutopia.org/discussion/reading-profile-children-philippines>
- [28]. Sperry, D. E., Sperry, L. L., & Miller, P. J. (2018). Reexamining the verbal environments of children from different socioeconomic backgrounds. *Child development*.
- [29]. Weisleder, A., & Fernald, A. (2013). Talking to children matters: Early language experience strengthens processing and builds vocabulary. *Psychological science*, 24(11), 2143-2152.
- [30]. https://www.education.act.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0005/807431/150897-Building-a-Strong-Culture-of-Parent-School-Engagement_2.pdf
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325348961_PARENTAL_INVOLVEMENT_IN_THE_PHILIPPINES_A_REVIEW_OF_LITERATURES
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325348961_PARENTAL_INVOLVEMENT_IN_THE_PHILIPPINES_A_REVIEW_OF_LITERATURES
<https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/sunstar-pampanga/20151010/281659663871082>